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UDK: 340.13:347.189(497-15):340.5

347.189(497-15)

392.91(497-15)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19600019

The Regulation of Personal Names in the Western Balkan Countries: Similarities and Differences

The paper aims to present the similarities and differences in the regulation of the institute of the personal name of natural persons in the Western Balkan countries. By using the comparative approach, this paper presents three key aspects of the legal regime of the personal name of natural persons in the Western Balkans countries: its determination at birth, the conditions and procedures for its change, and the mechanisms of legal protection. The analysis demonstrates that the legal regulation of this institute in these countries is based on numerous similarities, i.e., on common foundational principles in its regulation. However, the analysis will clearly demonstrate that the regulation of personal names in these countries also contains certain specificities. The similarities largely stem from the comparable socio-economic conditions in which these countries develop, whereas the differences arise from the degree of acceptance of modern European legal standards, as well as from their respective legal traditions.

Keywords: personal name, similarities, differences, regulation.

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***REGULISANJE LIČNIH IMENA U ZEMLJAMA ZAPADNOG BALKANA:
SLIČNOSTI I RAZLIKE***

Cilj rada je da predstavi sličnosti i razlike u regulisanju instituta ličnog imena fizičkih lica u zemljama Zapadnog Balkana. Primenom uporednog pristupa, rad predstavlja tri ključna aspekta pravnog režima ličnog imena fizičkih lica u zemljama Zapadnog Balkana: njegovo određivanje pri rođenju, uslove i postupke za njegovu promenu, kao i mehanizme pravne zaštite. Analiza pokazuje da je pravno regulisanje ovog instituta u ovim zemljama zasnovano na brojnim sličnostima, odnosno na zajedničkim temeljnim principima u njegovom regulisanju. Međutim, analiza će jasno pokazati i određene specifičnosti u regulisanju instituta ličnog imena fizičkih lica u ovim zemljama. Sličnosti u velikoj meri proizilaze iz uporedivih društveno-ekonomskih uslova u kojima se ove zemlje razvijaju, dok razlike proizilaze iz stepena prihvatanja savremenih evropskih pravnih standarda, kao i iz njihovih konkretnih pravnih tradicija.

Ključne reči: lično ime, sličnosti, razlike, propisi.